

WELCOME TO
Semiannual GreenX3 Newsletter

**Ghibli-style portrait created with AI using ChatGPT Pro with DALL-E image generation (OpenAI, 02May 2025 version).*

In this newsletter you will find:

- DC/DNS Progress
- Typical PhD challenges
- Events participations
- Tips
- Past and upcoming events

Enjoy Reading!

In our third GreenX3 newsletter

Celebrating One Year of Sustainable Innovation 🌱

As we mark the first anniversary of GreenX3, this special edition offers a moment of reflection on our progress, achievements, and the exciting road ahead. What began as a visionary idea has developed into a collaborative platform driving innovative, sustainable solutions with real-world impact.

Over the past year, GreenX3 has advanced through cutting-edge research, strategic partnerships, and a shared commitment to addressing environmental challenges. From developing greener materials to applying eco-conscious technologies, our initiatives exemplify how science and sustainability go hand in hand.

This edition highlights ongoing projects that are shaping our mission and demonstrates the critical role of EU-funded support in enabling progress. Backing from the European Union has been instrumental in transforming ambitious goals into tangible results, helping GreenX3 contribute meaningfully to a more sustainable future.

We invite you to explore the insights and updates within this issue and hope you draw inspiration from the collective dedication that defines the GreenX3 community.

[GreenX3](#)

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It has been an exciting year since I started my project, and I'm proud of the significant improvements I have made in extracting cholesterol from fish oil byproducts. At MyBiotech, I have had the opportunity to gain valuable industry skills, broaden my perspectives, and adopt new mindsets. These experiences are helping me shape and align my vision for the future and empowering me to make plans and eventually direct my own projects.

Key Highlights from My Project

Sustainable Innovation:

Converting waste into wellness with low environmental footprint

Market value:

Creating €-worth from what was once thrown away

Expertise :

Having a strong R&D and a vision to adapt to industry needs

European value:

A true example of how EU-funded research fuels sustainable growth

#3

From Fish Oil to Health One Year into the GreenX3 Journey

One year ago, I found myself standing over a cloudy flask of fish oil and ethanol, wondering: *could this waste really become something valuable?* At that time, it was just an idea like. Today, it's something much more. My project is not only proving that waste can be a resource, but also that it can be a steppingstone towards better health. At the heart of this project lies cholesterol; not as the problem it's often made out to be, but as a crucial starting point for something we all need: **Vitamin D3**.

Why does this matter?

Vitamin D3 deficiency affects over 1 billion people globally, contributing to weakened immune systems, poor bone health, and increased risk of chronic diseases. As the demand for supplements continues to rise, especially post-COVID, the global Vitamin D market is projected to exceed USD 1.5 billion by 2030. But current production methods are often resource-intensive and rely on non-renewable sources. *That's where my project offers a cleaner, smarter, and sustainable solution!* By extracting cholesterol from fish oil waste and purifying it up to **95% purity**, we create the essential starting material for Vitamin D3 synthesis without relying on environmentally harmful processes. It's a small but meaningful contribution to both public health and sustainability.

One Year of Journey in the Laboratory

Of course, this journey hasn't been linear. Over the past year, I have faced foaming emulsions, inconsistent separations, and unexpected chemistry quirks. I have learned that success doesn't always look like a single breakthrough. It's built on **small adjustments, careful observations, and creative problem-solving**. From tweaking solvent ratios to testing purification strategies, I have grown not only as a chemist, but as someone who now sees failure as feedback. *The work has taught me patience, persistence, and the power of keeping a green vision at the center of innovation.*

Looking Forward

As GreenX3 continues to evolve, its potential reaches beyond cholesterol or Vitamin D3. It's about transforming *how we view waste, design processes, and connect health with sustainability*. This is not just a lab project, but it is a glimpse of what greener biotech could look like in the future.

And that future? I'm excited to help shape it.

[LinkedIn](#)

May 2025

Shehneela JAMIL

Over the past months, the ongoing professional and personal exploration journey as a doctoral candidate has been nothing short of transformative.

Just like planting seeds is essential for growth and renewal,

An essential exploration of research questions is foundational for scientific development in research.

Because I believe,

The true challenge lies not in missing answers, but in missing the questions

This spring newsletter brings reflection on colorful perspectives and deeper understandings to reach the true questions in my research career.

Saarlouis

Uberherrn

Understanding my research questions

While actively pursuing effective development of drug delivery systems (DDS), one of the most important questions guiding my work is this: What are the green alternatives to the current processes in pharmaceutical manufacturing? This challenges me to evaluate the materials, methods, and protocols through a lens of **sustainability**.

Thus, demands a reframing of the current approaches and stepping towards the core idea of bringing sustainable solutions to this research project.

The reframing challenge has been addressed from various perspectives

That is accomplished through;

- ✓ Selection of green materials that are biocompatible and biodegradable
- ✓ Designing the synthesis protocol that does not involve toxic chemicals.

Isn't it green enough already? Maybe, but one must consider aspects of control, quality, and repeatability? This brings us to the subsequent phase of refinement.

- ✓ Employing continuous manufacturing technologies that not only intensify the process but also make it controlled and cost/energy-effective.

For this kind of control, doesn't it require defining Critical Process Parameters (CPPs)? What are CPPs, and how do we control them? Stay connected with me on this journey of finding the missing question.

Green on Screen

The GreenX3 winter workshop in January 2025 made me realize how magical this world is for a researcher. Considering the digital growth made based on the challenges of distance and difference. This workshop trained us on the effective use of digital resources and distance learning tools, *served its purpose to the fullest.*

GreenX3 – DC3

Supervisor: Prof. Rolf Müller
HIPS/UdS/MyBiotech - Saarbrücken, Germany

Elisa de Lannoy Guerra who I am?

Hi! I am Elisa, a chemist from Brazil and the DC3! During my master I studied in France, Germany and Poland. Professional wise, my interests are metabolomics, natural products, NMR and organic spectrometric techniques. By applying those interests to the pharmaceutical/biotechnology field, I hope to contribute for a healthier planet.

Currently, I am a MSCA doctoral candidate at Universität des Saarlandes / Helmholtz Institute for Pharmaceutical Research Saarland (HIPS) with secondment at MyBiotech GmbH.

Personal experience - moving around the globe

Living in a foreign country is not easy. It is constant learning. Things that can be obvious for locals are not for us - as our background is different. However, it gives us the opportunity to leave our bubble, getting to know people that you would never be able to meet, and finding out that life can be different than you thought, while at the same time realizing that humans have similarities regardless of where they come from.

Project progress – identifying the opportunities

As my project tackles three distinct aspects of novel microbial natural product discovery, the unique contributions of each approach are becoming clearer. By dividing the project aims into three–(1) evaluating greener analytical processes, (2) producing high-quality/quantity target material, and (3) characterizing compounds—we can better identify where each set (industrial vs. academic) adds the most value.

➤ Opportunities at the Industrial set

Improvement of isolation and production of natural products by

- **Extraction:** New technological tools (e.g. MicroJet Reactor)
- **Upscaling:** professional fermenters
- **Purification:** traditional techniques

➤ Opportunities at the academic set

Evaluation of analytical process and characterizing new structures by

- **Data-analysis:** highly advanced equipment for analyzing samples (e.g. MS and NMR)
- Essential for **initial screening and final characterization**

This overview highlights the benefits of having access to both academic and industrial set-ups with a common goal. The project is an example of how working in collaboration can enhance outcomes.

WHO BENEFITS WITH THIS RESEARCH?

Discovering new chemical structures derived from microbial production offers potential and opportunities to:

- **Research:** serve as a starting point for molecular engineering and synthesis
- **Pharmaceutical sector:** support the development of new drugs
- Mitigate infectious diseases in **Global South countries**
- **General health care:** fight issues related to drug resistance.

Metabolomics Data-Analysis Workshop

There is something truly valuable—something I deeply appreciate—about the MSCA grant: the **Career Development Plan**. It provides us with the opportunity to expand our know-how in areas that align with our interests.

Thanks to this, I had the chance to participate in a workshop on metabolomics data processing at the University of Cambridge.

Metabolomics data analysis is a crucial part of my project. It equips me with the tools to evaluate different techniques and identify secondary metabolites in my samples. Learning how scientists in various research groups conduct their analyses allows me to strengthen my specific knowledge and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the field.

I genuinely enjoyed seeing how others approach their work, and as a bonus, I also had the chance to meet my UK GreenX3 fellows!

Saad Ur Rehman who I am?

I am a Pharmacist from Pakistan. I completed Pharm-D from the University of Karachi and started my professional career as a formulation scientist in the pharmaceutical Industry in Pakistan. I did the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degree (EMJMD), in Nanomedicine for Drug Delivery from the University of Paris, University of Angers, University of Pavia, and University of Patras in France, Italy and Greece. I have a passion to work on the development of an innovative solution to prepare nanoparticles to load therapeutic molecules and improve pharmaceutical formulations. Following this passion, I joined Green X3 Project as a MSCA doctoral candidate at Saarland University.

Poster presentation at GreenX3 1st virtual workshop

Prof. Dr. Marc Schneider's Group at CRS Local Chapter Meeting in Bern, Switzerland.

Project progress

My PhD project focusses on improving the manufacturing process of nanoparticles so that it can be easily scaled up, moreover, it focusses on using sustainable material and making the process greener by reducing the cost and increasing the yield.

One of the biggest advantage I have in this industrial PhD is that I can work in both environments i.e., Academic and Industry. Which forces me to think about industrial translation early in my research. I have already had the privilege to go to industry and perform my experiments in industrial settings. I can say that this experience was very successful in understanding the system and the manufacturing process that I have been working on.

So far, I have been able to produce some positive results with greener manufacturing process using spinning disc system for nanoparticles preparation using some known synthetic polymers and a sustainable polymer that is extracted from Corn i.e., Maltodextrin. Using this sustainable polymer and green manufacturing process, we are very hopeful that,

 We will improve drug delivery by increasing encapsulation efficiency.

 We will improve the manufacturing process by reducing time and cost of the process.

 We will produce the sustainable formulation.

CRS Local Chapter – Bern 2025

I had the great opportunity to present my research work in highly renowned conference i.e., Controlled Release Society – Local Chapter, which was held in Bern, Switzerland.

It was a great opportunity to present a poster to like minded people from both academia and industry. Furthermore, I was also able to learn about other research groups and their progress in the same field.

Marta Vinha Vieira

Olá! I am a pharmacist and food technologist, originally from the beautiful island of Florianópolis, Brazil. I am currently pursuing an industrial doctorate as an MSCA Fellow at Nanomol Technologies and ICMAB/CSIC in Barcelona, under the framework of the GreenX3 project.

Curiosity has always driven me, guiding both my academic pursuits and personal adventures. I have been fortunate to experience life in various countries, each offering unique experiences. In my free time, I enjoy outdoor activities, travelling, reading, and spending quality time with loved ones.

Workshop - The Power of Virtual Reality

Nanomol Technologies Team

Innovating drug delivery for better patient care

Taking medicine over a long period can be hard, not just because of the disease itself, but because treatments can come with side effects or complicated routines. Many people struggle to keep up with their medications, especially when they don't feel well or must deal with uncomfortable injections or frequent doses.

In the GreenX3 project, one of my main goals is to help solve this problem by developing a new way to deliver medicine that is gentler, smarter and easier for patients to use – especially for those needing long-term care.

What is the idea?

Over the past year, I have been working on a special system that combines two exciting technologies:

- **Tiny drug carriers called nanovesicles** - Think of them as stable microscopic bubbles that carry medicine safely through the body.
- **A smart gel that changes with temperature** - It is liquid when injected but turns into a soft gel once inside the body. This gel stays under the skin and slowly releases the medicine over time.

Together, they form a kind of medicine depot under the skin. Instead of needing many doses or injections, this system can release the drug gradually, which helps keep it working longer, reduces side effects, and makes life easier for patients.

The first in-vitro tests with a model drug have gone really well, and the results were strong enough to support a patent application, which is a big milestone!

Why is it important?

- ✓ Enhances comfort and convenience;
- ✓ Reduces how often patients take medicine;
- ✓ Improves treatment adherence;
- ✓ Uses eco-friendly, sustainable technology.

What is next?

- ✓ Adapting the system to deliver sensitive medicines, like proteins and peptides. Though these treatments are complex to manage, improving their delivery could transform the way we treat chronic illnesses.

PhD Journey: Year 1

My first year of the PhD journey has been a rewarding mix of challenges and learning, each task pushing me to be more resourceful and innovative. This growth has been further enriched by living abroad, where I have had the chance to collaborate with an international team, adapt to a new culture, and strengthen my communication skills (working in Spanish!).

Overall, the journey is expanding my scientific knowledge and fostering personal growth. The challenges I have faced are teaching me how to adapt, navigate obstacles, and stay curious. As I move forward, I feel more prepared for the complexities of research and excited for the next steps in my project and career.

Nicolas Levrier

Hi, I'm Nicolas! I come from France, I was born and raised in the city of Marseille. I studied engineering and attended the Paris School of Chemistry, Chimie ParisTech-PSL. I graduated with a Master's degree in Integrative Chemistry.

My PhD journey started one year ago, at the Institute of Material Science (ICMAB-CSIC) in Barcelona, Spain. As part of the GreenX3 project, and in collaboration with the start-up company Nanomol Technology SL (Barcelona), my research aims to contribute to development of more sustainable nanotechnologies for the biomedical industry.

Personal Experience

One year into living in Barcelona, I'm happy to be diving deeper into the culture. Learning Spanish and using it daily has been a big step in that direction. Living in BCN as a PhD student also means navigating the flatshare market. The keypoint is to take every flat visit or moving with the enjoyment of a guided city tour.

Sagrada Família's inside stained windows

Project progress

➤ My Topic of Research

My research project is based on the design of advanced nanoparticles with inherent antimicrobial properties, to address the global health crisis of Antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

➤ Progress Update

Up to now, my work has focused on developing stable nanoparticle formulations to encapsulate special proteins, known as Antimicrobial Peptides. This unique combination is very promising to combat a wide range of infections. I performed a wide variety of antimicrobial tests, both against bacteria in suspension, and on surfaces where they group in even more resistant biofilms.

Antimicrobial testing "MIC": reading results of bacterial growth after incubation

Events Participation

- Poster Presentation during Junior PhD Gathering 2024, ICMAB, Barcelona

➤ Challenges PhD

One technical challenge I have faced is the limited supply of this protein. To address this, I chose to work with an antibiotic alternative.

Even if this initially sounded like a compromise, it actually opened up new research avenues, such as exploring combination therapies. Being flexible and adapting to available resources is certainly a keypoint for a PhD work!

- Virtual Poster Presentation during GreenX3 Workshop, Jan 25

I had the chance to participate in poster presentations both in person and in virtual reality. Although direct human connections remain irreplaceable, VR surprised me with its potential, the amazing tools and possibilities of engagement it provides!

GreenX3-DC7

Sara Spada

Good day readers!

I am Sara from Italy, a MSCA doctoral candidate currently based at the CNRS Enzyme and Cell Engineering laboratory at Université de Technologie de Compiègne (UTC) in France! I am pursuing my PhD in bioengineering after having obtained bachelor and master degrees in Molecular and Medical Biotechnologies at the University of Verona.

During my studies I had the opportunity to move abroad thanks to the Erasmus + for study and now I am really pleased to be part of the GreenX3 network, being able to discover new environments and cultures and, most importantly, be part of a network which focuses on greener solution for technologies, materials and processes: the future for a more eco-friendly and sustainable research 😊

At Protera with Laure and Kyra

Supervisor: Prof. Karsten HAUPT and Dr. Aude CORDIN
Université de Technologie de Compiègne / CNRS

Project progress and industrial secondment

Understanding nature and the complex mechanisms behind it has always been one of the main motivations that make scientific research move forward. My PhD project is not an exception: getting inspired by the natural specific molecular recognition between antibody-antigen I am trying to develop Molecularly Imprinted Polymers (MIP) with high specificity and selectivity for a target molecule.

So far, thorough optimization was done to improve the synthesis of MIP nanoparticles starting from the identification of suitable template molecules for the imprinting process by relying on a rational approach. MIP nanogels were obtained, and target binding tests showed promising results with the MIP binding to the target molecule better than a control non-imprinted polymer. Throughout this optimization, I faced challenges that required critical thinking, helping me develop knowledge and expertise.

As part of this PhD journey with the GreenX3 network, I started in November 2024 my secondment with our industrial partner Protera. Protera is a start-up company focusing mainly on protein engineering and artificial intelligence; the aim of our collaboration with them is to develop a sustainable strategy to sequester and remove a tag protein (TP) for a better, easier and eco-friendly purification of their protein production: this is where MIP technology comes to play!

1st Year as MSCA student: Events and Activities

All along my first year as a PhD student, I had numerous opportunities to disseminate my research. In this newsletter, I would like to report an outreach events to which I took part: the PhD day organized within our GEC laboratory. This is an annual event where all PhD students and post-doctoral researchers in our department are invited to present their research projects.

Nevertheless, learning and training to get new expertise and knowledges is a crucial step of the path that a PhD student has to follow to achieve the final objectives. The GreenX3 network offers multiples training and learning activities, such as the winter school we had in January 2025 about 'the Power of Virtual Reality'.

Presenting at the GEC PhD Day but not only...

-December 2024-

...reaching out thanks to the Power of the Virtual Reality!

-January 2025-

Kyra Magdato

Bonjour! I am Kyra, from the Philippines. 🇵🇭 I finished my bachelor and master's in chemistry at the University of the Philippines-Diliman while working as a science research specialist. I am currently based at the CNRS Enzyme and Cell Engineering Laboratory at the Université de Technologie de Compiègne pursuing a PhD degree in bioengineering. When I'm not in the lab, I enjoy yoga, reading a good book, and wall climbing.

In this newsletter, I am sharing a short update and introspective take on my first year as a PhD student and an introduction of my industrial secondment with the company Protera.

GEC PhD Day 2024

GreenX3 1st Workshop

A nature walk to Protera...

PhD Year 1: Progress and Introspection

Challenges on product storage, tracking, and inaccurate quality monitoring lead to premature disposal posing problems of waste accumulation. My PhD thesis aims to propose a solution to mitigate waste accumulation by fabricating a sensor based on molecularly imprinted polymers (MIP) to ensure *in situ* quantitative product quality assessment. During the first year, I've been working on designing and optimizing a method for the fabrication of the MIP-based sensor for one of our target protein. Modifications on the composition and protocol have been my focus and now, we have a protocol to prepare our MIP-based sensor and evaluate it.

Currently, we are assessing the sensor performance in environments mimicking different parameters for their potential application. Initial data yielded promising results and we are optimistic that this can be translated into actual product packaging materials for a non-invasive quality monitoring system.

The past year of doing my PhD has made me grow not only as an early-stage researcher in terms of scientific skills and knowledge, but more importantly, gave me a deeper understanding of how a study can contribute to the development of systems and technologies. However, doing a PhD is not all rainbows and butterflies, there are setbacks and detours. Overcoming these require assessment and critical thinking, but with the right approach coupled with good supervision from your mentors, the study can be directed and redirected to where it should be headed.

Industrial Secondment with Protera

In November 2024, Sara (DC 7) and I officially started our industrial secondment at Protera under the supervision of Laure Coulomb and Mathilda Freytet. Protera is a start-up biotech company focused on developing proteins for sustainable solutions using generative artificial intelligence, computational biology, and protein engineering.

The aim of my project during the industrial secondment is to design and optimize encapsulation techniques for the peptide of interest to improve their stability and release properties of their bioactivity. We are now focused on determining the methods we will employ for the encapsulation and ultimately to apply them to food and other products.

Akshay Ranganath

Warm welcome dear readers, this is Akshay Ranganath a scientist from India currently based in Italy working as a doctoral candidate under GreenX3 project. In my last page I had toured you all through my research objectives and industrial secondments, in this page I will talk about my research updates and challenges faced during the investigations. Soon after experiencing secondments at Demus S.p.A, I began to explore the polymerizations of natural monomers which was not as easy as it looked. Lots of pre-screening's were performed to choose a green monomer capable to polymerize effectively.

Exploiting an ingredient of cinnamon

In order to obtain polymers with adsorbent properties, a natural feedstock from cinnamon namely a cinnamate ester was subjected for different types of polymerization techniques. Eventually, with appropriate quantities of initiators & cross linkers, polymerization conditions were successfully developed. The different polymers synthesized were basically characterized by ¹H NMR & IR spectroscopy techniques. Furthermore, Thermogravimetric & Differential scanning calorimetric analysis were conducted to understand the thermal properties and Scanning Electron Microscopic images were carefully examined to understand the surface properties.

Trials & tribulations

The polymeric chains bearing ester moieties incurred a strong hydrophobic collapse resulting in decreased interaction with target molecules. To trouble shoot this extreme hydrophobicity, polymeric materials were subjected to surface saponification & acid hydrolysis. Regardless of the imposed surface modifications, eliminating the cause of hydrophobicity was totally challenging as we observed negligible interaction with the target compound.

Optimizations

Presently, a molecularly imprinted block polymer has been successfully synthesized using a commercial crosslinker which showed very good rebinding with the target compound. We are currently working to incorporate a new natural monomer (from an Aspergillus fungal source) in the ongoing polymerization technique to derive polymers with better rebinding capacity & reduced surface hydrophobicity.

Tribute to GreenX3

I whole heartedly admire the efforts of GreenX3 consortium for educating us with all the valuable training activities like international meetings ,workshops, winter& summer schools. Many thanks for the virtual reality workshop organized in Jan 2025, the immersive nature of virtual reality can significantly increase engagement and motivation, making it a powerful tool for education, training, and even entertainment.

Personal experience

It has been a year since I started working under GreenX3 as a doctoral candidate and I sincerely appreciate my supervisors for supporting my research through their valuable guidance and ideas. Participation in this project has taught me the importance of patience, resilience & perseverance to overcome the research obstacles and to think reflectively at every stage of it.

GreenX3-DC10

Supervisor: Prof. Cristina Forzato
The University of Trieste – Demus, Italy

Mandana
Chasing dreams

Hello everybody! I'm Mandana, a Persian woman who wants to discover the world and now, I'm lucky to be one of the members of this amazing project.

The other day, in one of my university courses, the lecturer asked: "What is your dream in life?" I answered that when I was a child, I dreamed of becoming a doctor or a chemist to create a magical substance that would keep people safe from disease. Today, I would say my dream is to become a good researcher who contributes to the betterment of our planet. But after class, I thought more about this question and I realized my biggest dream is even more personal: to help people and make their lives more beautiful. The best day for me is when I can make someone smile. That's my real dream - to bring joy to others, and maybe, just maybe, I can start by offering them a really good cup of coffee - one that's not only delicious but also good for their health ☺

Co-supervisor:
Prof. Federico Berti
Industrial Co-supervisor:
Dr. Yves Clyford Desobgo

Brewing better science ☺

Do you want to enjoy a cup of coffee before bed? Then you need decaf! And while you're sipping that smooth cup of decaffeinated coffee, rest assured - the caffeine that's been removed hasn't gone to waste. It can be repurposed into pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic products, thanks to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. I'm working to deliver a delicious, healthy decaf coffee while ensuring that caffeine finds a second life where it can still benefit people.

My work so far has focused on optimizing the decaffeination process by evaluating selectivity and efficiency under various conditions. A key part of this project is improving the safety of decaf coffee, particularly through arsenic removal. Although the arsenic content in decaffeinated beans is already below the regulatory limit, we're working toward removing as much of it as possible, as efficiently as we can, especially in organic decaf to ensure the highest possible quality and safety. To tackle this, I used one of the most abundant agricultural waste materials in Italy. After modifying its surface, I managed to remove a notable percentage of arsenic (V) from the beans. If we can scale this up to an industrial level, it could be a breakthrough. Not only would we be removing a toxic metalloid from food products, but we'd also be addressing the problem of agricultural waste disposal. These waste materials wouldn't be "waste" anymore - they'd become valuable filters for detoxification. The next step is to test the modified materials at the pilot plant in the company where I am currently doing my secondment. This will help determine whether this method is practical and economically viable at a larger scale. Fingers crossed!

Storms that shape us 🌱

This PhD journey has come with its own set of challenges-especially balancing the demands of academia with the realities of industry. In academic research, novelty and theoretical depth are priorities, often at a small scale. But in industry, practicality, scalability, and cost-effectiveness are key. It's a constant balancing act, but it's also the beauty of this type of PhD - we're not just publishing papers, we're creating solutions that can be used immediately in the real world.

From the lab to the world of coffee 🧪☺

It's now been almost a month since I started my secondment at Demus, our industrial partner. It feels like stepping into a whole new world. The very first thing that caught my attention as I approached the company was the aroma-an intense, earthy scent of green coffee beans. It's a totally different fragrance from what you get in your morning cup. That transformation, from green bean to roasted delight, is pure magic to me.

I've been warmly welcomed by a team of supportive and caring colleagues. Here, I should test my proposed materials for arsenic removal in the pilot plant-an exciting step toward practical application.

Looking ahead, I'll be attending the 30th ASIC conference on coffee science this October, and I couldn't be more thrilled. This international event brings together scientists, industry experts, and coffee lovers from around the globe to share innovations, research, and ideas around coffee-from bean to cup. I can't wait to see what I'll discover there!

Who is Megan, aka DNS11?

Hello! My name is Megan Gutman, and I am a Doctoral Network Candidate at Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). I obtained my B.Sc. in Chemistry from the University of Michigan (U-M), and my M.Sc in Chemistry from the Technical University of Munich (TUM). I'm passionate about key emerging technologies in green chemistry, which compliment my research interests in polymer and material science. When I'm not in the lab, you'll find me experimenting in the kitchen, traveling, or sweating at a HIIT class.

Simulating Sunlight: How do we age plastics in a lab?

One of my biggest research questions is: How do plastics break down in the natural environment? This is a tricky question to answer in research, because the environment is so fickle. One day the sun shines, the next it's gone; then it rains, then the wind knocks you over—and that's just London! Weather patterns vary across the globe and become less and less predictable with climate change. So how can we study plastic degradation with so many shifting variables?

In our group, we use artificial weathering chambers, which allow us to control variables, such as light intensity, duration, and the temperature during a 24-hour "day cycle." The light source we use simulates the broad spectrum of irradiation from the sun, which allows us to more closely replicate environmental conditions. So far, we have evaluated the effect of temperature, and the duration of light exposure per day cycle, which allows us to investigate the differences in plastic fragmentation in different geographical locations. The way that plastics break down may influence whether they persist in the environment as microplastics or continue to break down until they are biodegraded. For that reason, we're keen to investigate these degradation pathways to develop a tool to predict the environmental fate of commodity plastics.

Winter School Virtual Demonstration

Winter School Hololens Demonstration

Industrial Secondment at Symphony Environmental

"If it were easy, everyone would do it!"

This was the phrase my German host dad always said after a long day at work back in 2017—and it stuck with me! The path to a PhD is far from linear and shapes a scientist in unexpected ways. Before starting, you might think it's just lab work, results, a thesis, and done. But when that doesn't happen, it's easy to feel discouraged.

Luckily, many who've walked this path will say: what ends up on paper is only a small part of the degree. A PhD shows the ability to stay committed long after the novelty fades. It reflects critical thinking, deep engagement with new knowledge, and strong interpersonal skills—because science is rarely a solo act. It also shows project management, long-term planning, and adaptability when things change.

Challenges are chances to grow, and side quests can be surprisingly valuable. For example, I trained on an augmented reality device and demonstrated its use at our Winter School, *The Power of Virtual Reality*. As a group, we explored remote training methods and how such tech could support learning at a distance. Though not central to my research, it added a skill to my "green" toolbox—potentially helpful for reducing costs and carbon footprints in remote training or troubleshooting needs in future positions.

In the end, a PhD is as much about personal evolution as academic achievement. It's not just about what you study, but how you grow while doing it.

Eda

Greetings readers! I'm Eda, currently in London as a Doctoral Network Student at Queen Mary University of London (QMUL). Before settling in this vibrant city, I lived in izmir, Ankara, and Munich for my studies. Besides my academic pursuits, I'm passionate about exploring new destinations, immersing myself in the arts, and staying active with hobbies like ballroom dancing, yoga, and kayaking. These activities provide me with a sense of fulfilment and balance in life.

From Seaweed to Hope: My PhD Journey in London

Somewhere in the vast stillness of the ocean, a quiet solution grows. It does not shout. It does not pollute. It sways gently with the tides, asking for nothing but light and water. And yet it might help us solve one of the greatest environmental challenges of our time. 🌊🌱

This is where my journey began by questioning 'What if materials taken from nature could return to it without causing harm? What if the future of packaging could be rooted in nature itself?'

Over the past year, seaweed has become the centre of my world. I moved to London to begin a PhD that would explore how this marine organism could offer an alternative to the conventional plastics. A year ago, I barely knew the depth of the challenge. Today I still do not have all the answers, but I have learned how to ask the right questions.

Progress in a PhD is rarely linear. Sometimes it moves slowly. Sometimes it looks like failure before it becomes clarity. What seems straightforward at first often reveals layers of complexity. Seaweed from different regions behaves differently. Light, salt, season and environment all shape its structure. Even tiny differences affect how strong or flexible a material becomes. Learning to work with this natural variability has been one of the most eye-opening parts of my journey. It taught me that science is not just about precision and control, but about patience, observation, and embracing uncertainty.

At the same time, this journey has been full of people. Friends, mentors, fellow researchers. I never felt alone. The support of this community gave me the strength to face setbacks and keep moving forward with curiosity and care.

Now I'm entering a new phase. I will explore how these materials age, how they respond to environmental conditions such as sunlight, heat and time. My goal is simple – to help design materials that serve their purpose and then return to nature without harm.

This journey with seaweed has taught me that meaningful change often begins quietly. Not with grand gestures, but with questions. With observation. With care. I continue to follow where the tides lead, believing that even the softest movements can shape the future.

Connecting with Future Changemakers

**STEM
OUTREACH**

As part of my outreach activities, I had the opportunity to visit LAE Tottenham, a college in North London to talk about careers in Chemistry and Chemical Engineering. I engaged with curious and motivated students, sharing insights about my research journey and the role of science in tackling environmental challenges. Seeing their enthusiasm and thoughtful questions was inspiring enthusiasm and thoughtful questions, and I left with the strong belief that empowering young minds through open conversation can plant the seeds for a more sustainable and inclusive future.

Supervisor: Prof. Marina Resmini

Supervisor: Dr. Andre Gaduan

Timpy

Hi, I'm Timpy from India. I graduated in Analytical Chemistry from the University of Delhi in 2021, and my passion for addressing environmental issues led me to the Erasmus Mundus Master's in Environmental Contamination and Toxicology. This program allowed me to study at universities in France, Norway, Spain and Switzerland. I'm enthusiastic to implement my chemistry skills to tackle environmental challenges. In my free time, I enjoy hiking, cooking, exploring, celebrating cultures, and learning swimming, yoga, and photography.

Seaweed-based coatings- alternative to plastics?

How often do you go to the supermarket and think, "Why is everything—my food, vegetables, fruits—wrapped in so much plastic?" What if packaging could make us feel good instead of guilty of using too much plastic that often ends up polluting our land, ocean, air and impacts human health and environment? The key question I'm exploring in my PhD research is can packaging made from seaweed be a sustainable alternative to traditional plastic-based materials?

As part of my PhD research, I'm working on developing and evaluating these seaweed-based coating formulations. In my first year I had an exciting learning experience to prepare these coatings at Notpla. I've been learning how to evaluate their performance using various industry-relevant tests. For instance, I used the **contact angle instrument** and Cobb test to evaluate the water resistance, and applied the **KIT test**, and **pinhole test** to assess the oil barrier properties. While evaluating these coatings, I had experience of troubleshooting with contact angle instrument to develop and optimise the method for my materials. One of the most exciting parts has been using a **scanning electron microscope** to visualise the surface of the coatings I developed –giving me a detailed view of how these materials behave at the microscopic level.

Engagement Beyond Research

Alongside my research, I'm co-assisting the social media presence (especially Instagram) for our program, helping to create content, highlight achievements and foster connections within the community. I've also taken on the role of Student Health Representative at university, where I support peers and represent student voice in the Health and safety meetings. Additionally, I'm actively engaging with current students from my master's program by giving presentation on career paths and sharing insights about the Marie Skłodowska-Curie program. Through this session, I aim to motivate young scientists to pursue PhDs and explore diverse opportunities in research. These experiences have allowed me to contribute and grow beyond the academic setting, while giving back to the communities that shaped my journey.

DC Tips / suggestions

DC 1 - "Remember, if you're feeling lost, confused, and mildly panicked... you're probably doing it right. That's the PhD spirit. Just keep pretending you know what you're doing until your research agrees with you."

DC 2 - Connect, create, and celebrate the process.

DC 4 - Never worry about the results, always do your best and be honest.

DC 6 - Follow your curiosity, make time for your own training!

DC 8 - Make time for a hobby/sport. Life outside the lab matters too!

DC 10 - Every big discovery started with someone who didn't give up.

DNS 12 - Progress may be quiet and slow, but it's stronger than perfection. Remember to enjoy your journey!

DC 3 - Believe in yourself and always seek clarity and truth.

DC 5 - Time management is a must! Set aside a day each week to plan your tasks and goals for the upcoming week.

DC 7 - When you feel like giving up, always remember why you started

DC 9 - Stay calm, be focused & work smart

DNS 11 - Collaboration is key! The best learning opportunities come from your resource network.

DNS 13 - In the most uncertain times, try to stay calm. Let the storm pass and things cool down—Show up, you will figure it out.

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Past Events

PI Kick-Off Meeting
29.09.2023 | [Online](#)

DC Kick-Off Meeting
26.03.2024 | [Online](#)

Training on Team Building & Soft Skills
04.06. -05.06.2024 | [FMI](#)
MyBiotech, Überherrn - Germany

1st International Meeting
09.09. - 10.09.2024 | UNITS, Trieste - Italy

1st Summer School – Towards Green Materials
11 - 13.09.2024 | UNITS, Trieste - Italy

1st Workshop – The power of virtual reality
13.01 – 14.01.2025 | Online

Upcoming Events

2nd International Meeting
08-09.09.2025 | USAAR, MyB Germany

2nd Summer School
10-12.09.2025 | USAAR, MyB Germany

Thank you for reading!

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